

Table 1. Primary data information, 2020 and 2021. Times of recording are typically within 5min. TZ refers to Time Zone. GPS locations vary in resolution, from about 1m to about 30m. Camera spacing (*s*) and height above ground (*h*) are typically measured within 3cm.

ID	Date	Author(s)	Time	TZ	Location	State	GPS	<i>s</i> (m)	<i>h</i> (m)
s0521uf	20/05/21	RS	21:27	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	0.9	0.6
s0522uf	20/05/22	RS	21:00	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	0.9	0.6
s0523uf	20/05/23	RS	21:22	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	0.9	0.6
s0524uf	20/05/24	RS	20:43	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	1.8	0.6
s0525uf	20/05/25	RS	20:56	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	1.8	0.6
s0526uf	20/05/26	RS	20:59	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	1.8	0.6
s0527uf	20/05/27	RS	20:53	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	1.8	0.6
s0528uf	20/05/28	RS	20:49	EDT	Congaree National Park	SC	33.830, -80.818	1.8	0.6
s0601ic	20/06/01	RS	21:17	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN	35.65278, -83.57697	0.9	0.6
s0603ic	20/06/03	RS	21:47	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		0.9	0.6
s0606ic	20/06/06	RS	21:38	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		0.9	0.6
s0608ic	20/06/08	RS	21:41	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		1.8	0.9
s0609ic	20/06/09	RS	21:37	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		1.8	0.6
s0610ic	20/06/10	RS	21:40	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		1.8	0.6
s0611ic	20/06/11	RS	21:39	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		1.8	0.6
s0612ic	20/06/12	RS	21:37	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		0.9	0.6
s0613ic	20/06/13	RS	21:38	EDT	Great Smoky Mountains National Park, Elkmont	TN		1.8	0.6
s1601io	21/06/01	AO	20:45	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1602io	21/06/02	AO	20:40	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1604io	21/06/04	AO	21:10	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1605mx	21/06/05	AO	21:10	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1606mx	21/06/06	AO	20:50	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1607mx	21/06/07	AO	21:00	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1609mx	21/06/09	AO	21:05	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1610mx	21/06/10	AO	21:15	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1612mx	21/06/12	AO	21:15	EDT	Smith-Andover Land, Lincoln	MA	42.425769, -71.306571	1.0	0.6
s1613uf	21/06/13	PS	21:30	EDT	Black Oak Ridge Conservation Easement	TN		0.9	0.6
s1613io	21/06/13	AO	21:10	EDT	Muster Field, Lincoln	MA	42.427216, -71.315740	1.0	1.1
s1614ig	21/06/14	AO	20:20	EDT	Muster Field, Lincoln	MA	42.426305, -71.314495	1.0	0.6
s1615ux	21/06/15	AO	21:10	EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.441126, -71.375598	1.0	0.6
s1615uf	21/06/15	PS	21:30	EDT	Roane County	TN		0.9	0.6
s1617uf	21/06/17	PS	21:30	EDT	Oak Ridge Wildlife Management Area	TN		0.9	0.6
s1617ux	21/06/17	AO	21:20	EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.438924, -71.375985	1.0	0.6
s1618ux	21/06/18	AO	21:10	EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.438924, -71.375985	1.1	0.6
s1619ux	21/06/19	AO	21:10	EDT	Mattison Field, Concord	MA	42.438924, -71.375985	1.2	0.6
s1706ig	21/07/06	AO	20:30	EDT	Estabrook Woods	MA	42.485152, -71.346347	1.5	1.1
s1710im	21/07/10	AO	20:25	EDT	Drumlin Farm Wildlife Sanctuary, Lincoln	MA	42.407523, -71.330734	1.6	0.6
s1711im	21/07/11	AO	20:25	EDT	Drumlin Farm Wildlife Sanctuary, Lincoln	MA	42.407676, -71.331342	1.7	0.6
s1723im	21/07/23	AO	20:25	EDT	Drumlin Farm Wildlife Sanctuary, Lincoln	MA	42.407676, -71.331342	1.9	0.6
s1806ik	21/08/06	RS	20:00	MST	Pajarito Mountains, Coronado National Forest	AZ	31.394, -111.090	1.8	0.6
s1809ik	21/08/09	RS	20:30	MST	Pajarito Mountains, Coronado National Forest	AZ	31.394, -111.090	1.8	0.6
s1810ik	21/08/10	RS	20:45	MST	Pajarito Mountains, Coronado National Forest	AZ	31.394, -111.090	1.8	0.6
s1813ik	21/08/13	RS	23:00	MST	Pajarito Mountains, Coronado National Forest	AZ	31.394, -111.090	1.8	0.6